

Acidity Functions of Indicators for High pH in Non-aqueous Medium. Part-II

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The azo dyes α -(*o*-carboxyphenylazo)-*p*-nitrobenzyl cyanide (OCPNBC); α -(*p*-carboxyphenylazo)-*p*-nitrobenzyl cyanide (PCPNBC), α -(*m*-sulphophenylazo)-*p*-nitrobenzyl cyanide (MSPNBC) and α -(*p*-sulphophenylazo)-*p*-nitrobenzyl cyanide (PSPNBC) have been studied as new acid-base indicators. Two indicators are with COOH group and two are with SO₃H group. Investigations are carried out in methanol and the methodology has been reported elsewhere¹. All measurements were carried out in non-aqueous media.

Results and Discussion

All the four indicators reported exist as molecular species in acidic media. All are yellow in colour and their absorption maxima are within the range 410–420 nm. Extinction coefficient values for molecular species follow the order : PSPNBC > PCPNBC > OCPNBC > MSPNBC. Mono-anionic species are formed as the pH is increased.

The p*K* values are in order : MSPNBC > PCPNBC > PSPNBC > OCPNBC. The first isobestic point lies in short wavelength region and the second isobestic point is in the visible region. Extinction coefficient values of indicators in methanol are sufficiently high (Table 1). The results show that there is equilibrium between molecular and monoanionic and dianionic species. Absorption maxima are in range 410–420 nm for molecular species 510–570 nm for monoanionic species and 530–540 nm dianionic species.

The linearity of pH against absorbance plot in all cases indicate that the indicators are useful for colourimetric estimation.

The stock solutions of indicators did not show any measurable change over a period of one year and are quite stable. The solution in butter alkaline system showed stability for several hours, thus enabling one to have sufficient time for experimental measurements.

TABLE 1—ABSORPTION CHARACTERISTICS AND IONISATION CONSTANTS ACIDITY FUNCTIONS IN METHANOLIC SODIUM METHOXIDE

Indicator	Mono-anionic p <i>k</i> ₁	Di-anionic p <i>k</i> ₂	λ_{\max} nm/(ϵ_{\max})			Colour change	Isobestic point nm		H ^M ₋	H ^M ₂₋
			Molecular	Mono-anionic	Di-anionic		(1)	(2)		
OCPNBC	14.13	16.62	420 (6.5 × 10 ⁴)	580 (1.5 × 10 ⁴)	610 (1.0 × 10 ⁴)	Yellow to green to violet	400	470	14.05–15.04	16.49–17.60
PCPNBC	13.50	16.55	410 (1.1 × 10 ⁴)	570 (6.0 × 10 ⁴)	530 (4.9 × 10 ⁵)	Yellow-red to violet	460	460	13.70–14.48	16.03–17.30
MSPNBC	13.13	16.14	410 (7.9 × 10 ⁴)	570 (3.7 × 10 ⁴)	640 (1.4 × 10 ⁵)	Yellow to green to violet	400	470	12.39–14.00	15.36–16.59
PSPNBC	13.37	16.00	410 (1.1 × 10 ⁴)	510 (1.1 × 10 ⁴)	510 (5.0 × 10 ⁴)	Yellow to red to violet	460	430	13.05–14.40	14.78–16.50

Acidity functions were theoretically calculated on the basis of use of autoprotolysis constant of methanol and ethanol H_2^M values calculated from the spectral data. The theoretical acidity functions are plotted in the above show the order to know agreement between and practical values. From the plot it can be seen that H^M functions cover the range 12.3–15.04 and H_2^M cover the range 14.7–17.6. It is observed that first ionisation of OCPNBC, MSPNBC, PCPNBC and PSPNBC prove to be useful set for colorimetric determination.

Acidity functions in methanolic sodium methoxide, H^M and H_2^M corresponding to first and second proton loss are evaluated and presented in Table 1.

Experimental

α -(*o,p*-Carboxyphenylazo)-*p*-nitrobenzylcyanide : A solution of *o*- or *p*-aminobenzoic acid (1.37 g, 10 mmol) in warm HCl was diazotised by sodium nitrite. A solution of *p*-nitrobenzyl cyanide (1.62 g, 10 mmol) in ethanol (110 ml) was then slowly added to it. The mixture was stirred for 5 min,

kept at room temperature and neutralised with 1M NaOH. A green compound was obtained which was purified on alumina column, m.p. 196° (Found : C, 57.8; H, 3.8; N, 17.5. $C_{15}H_{12}O_4N_2$ requires : C, 57.7; H, 3.9; N, 17.9%).

The indicators were prepared according to the procedure in literature³. A 0.05% (w/v) solution of the indicators was prepared. The sodium methoxide of various concentrations were prepared to adjust the desired pH. The final concentration of indicator was 1.6×10^{-5} M. Absorption spectrum of each indicator was taken on a Beckman DU2 spectrophotometer using 10 mm glass cuvettes to determine the ratio of anionic and molecular forms from which the pK values was calculated⁴.

A Radiometer pHM4 pH meter was used.

References

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